

DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN AGRICULTURE: CRITERION OF
POPULATION WELFARE

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Abstract. Agriculture is one of the most important industries in the world. It can be said that it feeds all people. But in addition, it provides labor resources with many jobs, the emergence of which creates new economic relations in the process of economic integration in the entrepreneurship and agricultural sector. Entrepreneurship in the modern world, especially in agriculture, farmers and peasant farms, homestead land owners face a number of problems, difficulties and obstacles due to the specific characteristics and risks associated with this business. The relevance of this topic is determined by the need to form highly efficient, competitive and quality entrepreneurship in agriculture.

Key words: entrepreneurship, entrepreneur, agriculture, new economic relations, economy, efficiency, problems, development prospects, potential.

РАЗВИТИЕ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ:
КРИТЕРИЙ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Сельское хозяйство является одной из важнейших отраслей промышленности мира. Можно сказать, что оно кормит всех людей. Но кроме того, оно обеспечивает трудовые ресурсы множеством рабочих мест, появление которых создает новые экономические отношения в процессе экономической интеграции в сфере предпринимательства и сельского хозяйства. Предпринимательство в современном мире, особенно в сельском хозяйстве, фермеры и крестьянские хозяйства, приусадебные землевладельцы сталкиваются с рядом проблем, трудностей и препятствий, обусловленных спецификой и рисками, связанными с этим бизнесом. Актуальность данной темы определяется необходимостью формирования высокоэффективного, конкурентоспособного и качественного предпринимательства в сельском хозяйстве.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, предприниматель, сельское хозяйство, новые экономические отношения, экономика, эффективность, проблемы, перспективы развития, потенциал.

Enter. Entrepreneurship or business (English: business - "employment") refers to any legal commercial activity. A person engaged in business is called an entrepreneur. Private enterprise is the basis of a capitalist economy. In socialist economies, entrepreneurship is handled by the government, society, or labor unions.

According to Article 24 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan called Entrepreneurship of a Citizen, a Citizen has the right to engage in entrepreneurial activity from the moment of state registration as an individual entrepreneur. The provisions of this Code shall be applied to the business activities of citizens without establishing a legal entity, unless a different procedure is understood from the legislation or the nature of the legal relationship [1].

A citizen who violates the requirements of the first part of this article, without establishing a legal entity, does not have the right to pretend that he is not an entrepreneur in the transactions concluded. The court may apply the provisions of this Code on obligations related to the implementation of business activities to such transactions.

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-328 dated May 2, 2012 "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity" in the new version states that Entrepreneurial activity (entrepreneurship) is carried out by the subjects of entrepreneurial activity in accordance with the law. , is defined as entrepreneurial activity aimed at obtaining income (profit) at one's own risk and under one's own property responsibility [2].

Thus, it is possible to form definitional interpretations that combine the previous ones. Entrepreneurship is an activity aimed at satisfying independent economic needs, an activity aimed at obtaining profit through competitive advantage.

Study of the topic. The first scientific studies of entrepreneurship were carried out by economists R. Cantilon, A. Turgot, F. Kene, A. Smith, J. B. Sey and others in the 18th century. The conclusion is that the concepts of "entrepreneur" and "entrepreneurship" were introduced into economic relations during this period. Later, such research expanded and began to develop as a separate scientific direction, and the practical application of their results has an effective impact on the economy. One of such results is the definition and enrichment of the concept of "entrepreneurship". U. Schumpeter, a representative of the new Austrian school, plays an important role in the scientific and practical analysis of entrepreneurship in the 20th century. It

determines the role of entrepreneurship in the dynamic economic process, its creative function, draws the psychological image of an entrepreneur. According to him, the entrepreneur is considered as the main driving force of the economy. Relevance of the topic.

According to Asaul A.N. [3], entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity; its essence is to stimulate and meet the specific demands of society through the market, the needs of its members through the exchange and distortion of the competitive advantage market equilibrium.

According to I. V. Ukrainitseva [4], the subjects of entrepreneurship are the entrepreneurs who operate the business and take full responsibility.

In the book "Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship", the processor U. Gafurov defines an entrepreneur as a person who has the ability to do business, that is, the knowledge, skills and experience in organizing some kind of goods production or service process [5].

For the successful development of entrepreneurship, agriculture must take into account the characteristics determined by the specific characteristics of the process of production in this area. These characteristics include, first of all, the fact that, as mentioned above, the main means of production is land. Using it correctly is the key to success. Relatively, they require careful use, compliance with environmental requirements and standards, and also increase fertility. Because the land is the main thing in agricultural production, then it refers to the second characteristic connected with climatic conditions. The climate can be different depending on the possible types of agriculture, activities specific to this or that type of climate. For example, if it is in a tropical climate, wheat, cocoa and coffee grow, then in a temperate climate - citrus fruits, grapes, olives.

In addition, the rural economy depends on natural phenomena. Thus, sudden changes in weather conditions can lead to a decrease in the volume of the harvest or even its loss.

Also, seasonality of production and labor is included in the natural features of agriculture. The production cycle in this industry depends entirely on the time of year. Due to the cyclical development of plants and animals, seasonality is an inevitable factor.

Another characteristic feature is the perishable nature of the products. In this regard, its implementation must be done in a timely manner, otherwise any delays can lead to damage to the goods and difficulties in sales.

It is necessary to take into account the economic factors affecting entrepreneurial activity in agriculture. Thus, a ban on the export of any product leads to the fact that the manufactured product cannot be sold, and the entrepreneur suffers accordingly. It is also necessary to take into account the constant changes in market conditions, prices, demand and supply levels.

Agriculture is the main source of food for the population of different countries and cities. Specific features of the agricultural industry allow it to influence entrepreneurship and its efficiency. Taking these features into account and using modern technologies, entrepreneurs can improve production, increase labor productivity, and strengthen their financial situation.

In any field of activity, there are a number of problems and obstacles that prevent its development and prosperity. They appear for completely different reasons and in completely different directions. But thanks to them, the shortcomings of the system are visible, which makes it possible to correct them and improve the system as a whole.

The field of entrepreneurship in agriculture is no exception. Currently, there are a number of problems that prevent the rapid development of entrepreneurship both globally and in Uzbekistan.

Science-based suggestions and recommendations. There are specific problems of entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan. Thus, the main problem can be called personnel, both from the lack of personnel and from their professional training. The modern development of agriculture is based on the latest achievements of science and new technology, which requires a certain classification of employees.

The second problem is related to small business in agriculture. They lack capital to improve production. Credit services are mainly suitable for large manufacturers. Small business entities have to collect a lot of documents, conduct expertise and perform many unnecessary actions in order to receive state support. This reduces the availability of credit for them. In addition, there is a problem of lack of investment in the long term.

All this leads to another problem - product quality. Some types of products are inferior in quality to their counterparts in other countries, so they sell less products from local producers and prefer better products.

Thus, there are unsolved problems in agricultural business both globally and in individual countries. But these problems help us to see the flaws or shortcomings, and allow us to find new ways to develop and create new high-performance technologies.

The business perspective is to improve production efficiency. Expanding the use of the latest technologies allows not only to produce more products in a short time, but also to significantly improve their quality. In addition, the growth of technical and technological capabilities will only serve the development of agriculture and entrepreneurship.

The next direction of development is international cooperation. These are. Developing countries receive support from developed countries in providing material and financial support, as

well as in learning their business practices and methods. This will help to eliminate the backwardness of some countries and agricultural structures, and to determine their potential.

In conclusion, we can say that at present, agriculture, like any branch of the economy, has its own problems that prevent its rapid development and improvement. But in their study, many promising directions for strengthening positions and further growth are emerging.

Due to the fact that entrepreneurship in agriculture is widespread throughout the world, it creates many opportunities for international cooperation. There is no doubt that this will be useful both for individual countries, in accelerating their development and unlocking their potential, and in bringing it to a new level in the entire world economy.

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